

THOT THEORY OF TONE

Dmitry Gerasimov

Dom. Analytical report on the tonal system

DOI [10.5281/zenodo.14751314](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14751314)

0. This analytical report follows Questionnaire version 8d. It is fully based on (Tida 2006).

1. General information about the language

1.1. Language name

Dom

ISO-639: doa, Glottolog: domm1246.

1.2. Genetic affiliation and distribution

Simbu < Chimbu-Wahgi < Nuclear Trans-New-Guinean

Geographic area: Simbu province, Papua New Guinea.

Number of speakers: ca. 12000 in 1994, according to (Eberhard, Simons & Fennig 2024). Tida (2006: 10) gives a rough estimate of 16000 for the entire ethnic group.

1.3. Dialects

The Dom people are divided into at least 8 clans, with minor dialectal differences between them that do not hinder mutual intelligibility (Tida 2006: 3–4). Tida’s data primarily come from members of the Non Ku clan, although speakers from other clans were also consulted. While the dissertation does not provide a systematic survey of dialectal variation, it contains numerous remarks on specific differences, mostly pertaining to phonetics and lexicon.

Glottolog recognizes two dialects of Dom: Nuclear Dom (nucl1817) and Era (eraa1239). Tida treats the latter somewhat inconsistently, introducing it as a separate language, Dom’s closest relative (2006: 4), but sometimes mentioning it among clan dialects of Dom.

For bookkeeping purposes, (Tida 2006) and, by extension, this report can be said to cover Nuclear Dom.

1.4. Relevant publications

(Tida 2006) is the only description of Dom, with its phonology chapter superceding the author’s Japanese-language MA thesis (Tida 2000). Data of the Dom tonal system is also featured in an unpublished conference paper (Tida 2012).

2. Segmental phonology

2.1. Phonemic inventory

2.1.1. Vowels

2.1.1.1. Vowel inventory

i	u
e	o
a a:	

Table 1. Dom monophthongic vowels (Tida 2006: 9)

Dom possesses five vowel qualities; only /a/ has a long counterpart. Vowels bearing a contour tone undergo phonetic lengthening to accommodate it.

In addition, there are diphthongs /ai/, /au/, /ae/, /ei/, /eu/, /ea/, /oi/, /oa/, /ia/, /io/, /iu/, /ui/, /uo/, /ua/. Tida (2006) calls them “vowels sequences”, but clearly treats them as tautosyllabic. Only /ai/ and /au/ (and maybe also /eu/, the wording is not quite clear) have wide distribution; all other diphthongs are confined to word-initial syllables and may have other restrictions on their occurrence. /ae/ is only found in one, albeit presumably highly frequent native morpheme, the mutual knowledge clitic =*râe* MUT. Many diphthongs have a range of phonetic realizations; some may alternate with plain vowels, e.g. [au] ~ [o] or [ae] ~ [æ] (the default realization).

Importantly, sonorants (/m/, /n/, /r/, /l/) can also be syllabic.

There is a non-phonemic [i] inserted within consonant clusters.

There are no correlations between vowel quality and tone.

2.1.2. Consonants

2.1.2.1. Consonant inventory

		Bilabial	Alveolar	Alveopalatal	Velar
Stops	voiceless	p	t		k
	prenasalized	b [ʰb]	d [ʰd]		g [ʰg]
Nasals		m	n		
Affricates	voiceless			(c [tʃ])	
	prenasalized			(j [ʰtʃ])	
Fricative			s		
Lateral(s)			l		(L)
Flap			r [ɾ]		
Approximants		w		y [j]	

Table 2. Dom consonants (Tida 2006: 13)

Table 2 presents the 16 consonants of Dom. Those in parentheses only occur in loanwords; some speakers may substitute them with native phonemes.

Voiceless stops /p/ and /k/ appear as corresponding voiced fricatives [β] and [ɣ] in intervocalic position. Most other consonants also have a range of phonetic realizations that may differ somewhat between dialects.

Consonants have no impact on the realization of tones. Consonant quality does not affect the limits of tonal spans. It must be noted, however, that only verbs with stems ending in -Vl or -Vr can have a lexical HL toneme (see §8.2 on the tonal classes of verbs).

2.2. Prosodic units

2.2.1. Syllable and mora

Dom possesses a wide range of syllable types (Tida 2006: 21–22). The following structures are found in monosyllabic words and in final syllables of longer words (with C standing for any consonant other than w)¹:

- | | | | |
|-----|--------|--|-----------------|
| (1) | C | <i>d̂</i> ‘to say’ | |
| | CC | <i>n̂l̂</i> ‘water’, <i>p̂ř</i> ‘flying’ | |
| | CCC | <i>b̂řm</i> (place name), <i>m̂řm</i> ‘husbands sister, brother’s husband (from female)’ | |
| | (C)V | <i>ká</i> ‘word’, <i>ǒ</i> ‘hand’ | |
| | (C)wV | <i>gwě</i> ‘to take out’ | |
| | (C)VV | <i>ái</i> ‘place’, <i>tǎu</i> ‘some’ | |
| | (C)VC | <i>óp</i> ‘handle’, <i>tép</i> ‘on the top’, <i>âl</i> ‘dog’, <i>kǎl</i> ‘thing’ | |
| | (C)VVC | <i>yâum</i> ‘his grandfather’, <i>pǎim</i> ‘they sleep’ | (Tida 2006: 21) |

Thus, Cw is the only possible cluster in the onset and no complex codas are allowed. Normally, no CC-final words can be monosyllabic, cf. *kó.r̂m̂* ‘he discards’, *yà.u.l̂ĥ* ‘you open’².

CwVC syllables can be found in any position within a polysyllabic word:

- | | | |
|-----|------|---|
| (2) | CwVC | <i>yò.gwál</i> ‘where s/he put’, <i>gwèp.ké</i> ‘we two take out’ (Tida 2006: 21) |
|-----|------|---|

Syllables with complex codas are restricted to non-final positions within polysyllabic words. They arise when a C-final root is followed by a suffix starting with a consonant cluster, such as *-krae* MUT.

- | | | |
|-----|----------|---|
| (3) | (C)VCC | <i>kàrp.ké</i> ‘we two see’, <i>kórp.gè</i> ‘we discard’ |
| | (C)VVCC | <i>bàulp.ké</i> ‘we two trick’, <i>yàulp.gé</i> ‘we open’ |
| | CCCC | <i>k̂ņpk.ráe</i> ‘we two carry, as we know’, <i>è.k̂ļpk.ráe</i> ‘we two split firewood, as we know’ |
| | CCw | <i>p̂řw.dàe</i> ‘he knows, as we know’ |
| | CCCw | <i>k̂ņgw.ráe</i> ‘he carries, as we know’, <i>kù.k̂ļgw.ráe</i> ‘he hugs, as we know’ |
| | (C)VCCC | <i>kàrp̂k.ráe</i> ‘we two see, as we know’, <i>àlp̂k.ráe</i> ‘we two stand, as we know’ |
| | (C)VVCC | <i>bàulp̂.dáe</i> ‘we trick, as we know’, <i>bàulk̂.ráe</i> ‘I trick, as we know’ |
| | (C)VVCCC | <i>bàulp̂k.ráe</i> ‘we two trick, as we know’ |
| | (C)Vw | <i>náw.dàe</i> ‘he goes, as we know’, <i>pàw.dáe</i> ‘he sleeps, as we know’ |
| | (C)VCw | <i>mólw.dàe</i> ‘he stays, as we know’, <i>kànw.dáe</i> ‘he sees, as we know’ |
| | (C)VVw | <i>pàiw.dáe</i> ‘they sleep, as we know’, <i>mo.làiw.dáe</i> ‘they will stay, as we know’ |
| | (C)VCCw | <i>mólgw.dàe</i> ‘he stays, as we know’ |
| | (C)VVCw | <i>bàulw.dáe</i> ‘he tricks, as we know’ |
| | (C)wVCC | <i>gwèpk̂.ráe</i> ‘we two take out, as we know’ |
| | (C)wVw | <i>gwèw.dáe</i> ‘he takes out, as we know’, <i>wèw.dáe</i> ‘he cuts, as we know’ |
| | (C)wVCw | <i>gwègw.ráe</i> ‘he takes out, as we know’, <i>wègw.ráe</i> ‘he cuts out, as we know’ |
| | wVCCw | <i>wèlgw.ráe</i> ‘he rolls, as we know’ |
- (Tida 2006: 21–22)

In short, possible syllable structures conform to the following templates:

¹ In (Tida 2006), reverse Chao tone letters are employed to indicate word-level melodies, while direct Chao tone letters are used in phonetic transcription to mark tones on individual syllables. I generally substitute the former with toneme brackets and the latter with diacritic marks, but sometimes cite phonetic transcriptions verbatim (with Chao letters), when warranted.

² There are, however, a few exceptional CVCC words arising as a result of (optional) metathesis (see §6.2.2)

- (4) a. C
 b. CÇ(C)
 c. CÇ(C)(C/w)
 d. (C)(w)V(V)C
 e. (C)(w)V(V)(C)(C)(C/w) (Tida 2006: 21–22)

The templates in (4c, e) are confined to non-final syllables of polysyllabic words. They are derived from those in (4b, d) respectively by allowing more complex codas. There are also less restrictions on the appearance of Cw onset clusters, although this is not reflected in the formula (4e).

Note that while syllables of the types summarized in (4b–c) necessarily have a syllabic sonorant as their nucleus, this is not true of monoconsonantal syllables in (4a). See shortly below.

The following principles (5) and rules (6) of syllabification are taken almost verbatim from (Tida 2006: 22–23):

- (5) a. A syllable should not cross over a word boundary.
 b. A vowel or a sonorant can be in the nucleus.
 c. A consonant can be an onset or a coda.
- (6) a. Only /w/ is allowed for the second part of onset clusters. (The onset should consist of only one consonant otherwise).
 b. A syllable cannot have a coda, if the following two segments form a possible onset-nucleus combination.
 c. If the preceding condition does not apply, a syllable can take the following consonant as a (part of its) coda.
 d. If the following segment is a vowel, take it as a nucleus.
 e. A sonorant is syllabic when it follows the onset of the syllable.
 f. [i] should be inserted and used as syllable nucleus when an obstruent follows the onset of the syllable.
 g. If the syllable still does not have a nucleus, /i/ is inserted after the onset.

The rules in (6) are apparently applied from left to right, although this is not stated explicitly in the text. Syllable boundaries in Dom often occur in somewhat unexpected places, e.g. *bná* ‘his/her hand’ is *bñ.á*, not **b^l.ná*. It is conceivable that faithfulness to morphological segmentation may play some role in syllabification, but there is no discussion of this issue in the grammar. I am thus not quite sure if e.g. *p-ré* ‘go-CONJ(SS)’ should be syllabified as *p^l.ré* or *p^r.é*. In this and similar cases I go for the latter option, which is more in line with the letter of the rules in (6). Luckily, the choice doesn’t affect the calculation of TDI or any other quantitative measure.

Insertion of non-phonological [i] can happen within any clusters consisting of obstruents or nasals, but it is only obligatory under the conditions specified in (6f). Only an obligatory [i] is syllabic and can carry tone. /i/-insertion in (6g) is mostly relevant for monoconsonantal words³. This epenthetic /i/ can be realized as [i], when the form containing it “is not phonetically set off from the following word”. Cf.:

- (7) [H *d*] [HL *pke*] → [n^ldí pi.kè] ~ [n^ldí pi.kè] ‘I hear’ (Tida 2006: 21)

³ The quotative clitic is alternatively transcribed as either =*d* or =*di* in (Tida 2006). I take this as to be an inconsistency in presentation rather than alternation between two different forms, with (purportedly phonetic) *i*-insertion sometimes being marked in the phonological transcription.

Syllabic sonorants are also given with an epenthetic short [i] in the phonetic transcription, though not always. Cf. [ᵐbʰɪ̯] ‘thigh.3SG.POSS’, [nʰi̯] ‘water’, [eʰkʰi̯] ‘far’ vs. [pɾi̯] ‘fly.INF’ (Tida 2006: 23, 24).

There is a difference in realization of tones on light vs. heavy syllables, though it is subtle and only relevant for word-final syllables. When a HL toneme is mapped onto a prosodic word, a falling contour is only formed on the last syllable if the latter is heavy (contains a long vowel /a:/, a diphthong, or a consonantal coda). Light syllables in monosyllabic words undergo lengthening to accommodate a HL or LH toneme; vowel length is not distinctive in this context, since long counterparts of vowels other than /a/ are not found anywhere else. (Polysyllabic words like *ámlâ*: ‘light’ (**ámlà*) testify that length distinction can be phonological, not arising from the need to accommodate a tonal contour). Tida (2006: 26–29) thus concludes that the TBU is the mora. Under his account, tonal association in Dom is ultimately moraic, but with an additional (violable) constraint against rising contours. Stricter limitations on the occurrence of rising contours are cross-linguistically common and are to be expected, as a rising tone takes more time to articulate than a falling tone of equal pitch excursion (Xu & Sun 2002; Zhang 2013).

However, while syllable weight is clearly relevant for the realization of tones⁴, there are no other weight-sensitive phenomena in Dom. Consequently, by the criterion adopted within the framework of the present project, the TBU is the syllable.

2.2.2. Foot

There seems to be no reason to postulate a prosodic foot in Dom.

2.2.3. Word

A prosodic word in Dom generally coincides with a morphological word consisting of a root which can be followed by one or more (in case of verbs) suffixes. Prosodic words are exhaustively segmented into syllables.

Voiceless stops /p/ and /k/ are usually realized as voiced fricatives in intervocalic positions within words, but not at the word boundary: *ike* [iʎeʰ] ‘house’, *kupa* [kuʎβa]. This provides a useful, albeit limited, diagnostic for wordhood. Prosodic words can also be separated by pauses and have no more than one tonal span each.

Dom possesses a number of enclitics that manifest properties of separate prosodic words⁵. Cliticization, unlike suffixation, never leads to resyllabification; clitics form their own tonal spans, and clitic-initial /p/ and /k/ are never fricativized. It must be noted, however, that consonant assimilation rules that apply at word-internal morpheme boundaries also operate across some clitic boundaries, but not across proper word boundaries. Tone on the host can also influence that on the clitic (§6.1.2), but at least similar tonal processes can affect adjacent words within a prosodic phrase that are not viewed as instances of cliticization (§6.1.3).

Reduplication (§7.1.3) in Dom is a word-level pattern, so a reduplicated form consists of two prosodic words that can have a pause inserted in-between and each carry its own toneme.

There are several lexemes, both nominal and verbal, that at first sight do not conform to the general tone association patterns and look like they contain more than one tonal span. These are best viewed as combinations of two separate prosodic words that do not occur independently (Tida 2006: 39–41): [H *ka*] [LH *kopa*] ‘bird’, [HL *kui*] [H *mol*] ‘morning/tomorrow’, [H *si*] [LH *ma-*

⁴ Note that this relevance is rather limited: only the weight of the word-final syllable affects tonal realization and only for one toneme (HL) out of three.

⁵ In fact, from the text of (Tida 2006) it remains unclear, e.g., what phonological and syntactic differences are there between =*tá* INDEF and *tá* ‘another’. On the other hand, it must be noted that cliticization of =*k(i)*- NEG, =*iâ* EXPL and =*iô* EXPL can be accompanied by segmental changes that are characteristic of a suffix rather than a clitic boundary (cf. §6.2). Tida (2006) uses the “+” sign (rather than “=”) specifically for these three clitics, but I do not follow this convention here.

gwe ‘wake.someone.up-3SG.IND’, [*H ma*] [*LH du-gwe*] ‘look.for-3SG.IND’. The presumed word boundary may contain phonemes that are not typical word-internally (such as /d/ in *du-gwe*) and when /p/ or /k/ is encountered in this position, fricativization doesn’t take place: [kaɫ.koɫ.βaɫ] ~ *[káɫ.ʏòɫ.βāɫ]. Also, importantly, with bipartite verbs, the reduplicated form used with the auxiliary *el-* involves repetition of only the second component: [siɫma:ɫma:ɫ] ~ *[siɫma:ɫsiɫma:ɫ]. Some bipartite nouns are frozen reduplications (cf. §7.1.3).

3. Tones and tonemes inventory

3.1. Character of the tonal system

The tone system of Dom combines levels and contours.

3.1.1. If it is a (predominantly) level-tone system, how many levels does it count?

The tone system of Dom is not level-based, but it can be said to employ two tonal levels: L and H. Only the latter forms a toneme by itself.

The grammar also makes reference to mid-level pitch (M), which is attested in the following environments:

- as a realization of a H tone in a LH melody/toneme (Tida 2006: 24–25);
- on the first syllable of a clitic following a H- or LH-toned word;
- optionally, on the first syllable of a verb form marked for future.

In the former case, M is best viewed as a downstepped H (see §3.4). In the latter two cases, the syllable in question is unspecified for tone (see §6.1.2 and §7.1.1 respectively) and its pitch is non-contrastive (either contextually determined or variable, see §4.3.1).

3.1.2. Are there contours hosted by one TBU?

Contours can only surface on heavy syllables, but short vowels in monosyllabic words can undergo phonetic lengthening to accommodate a contour tone.

3.2. Inventory of tonemes

Dom has three tonemes: H, LH and HL.

The **H toneme** is always realized as a high pitch on every TBU of its tonal span: *bñ* ‘thigh.3SG.POSS’, *ká* ‘word’, *gál* ‘rough’, *képí* ‘small’, *ékú* ‘afterwards’, *múkál* ‘bamboo sp.’, *árápí* ‘be cut.INF’, *nómáné* ‘think.INF’.

The tonemic status of H is confirmed by the following criteria:

– The Activity criterion: the H tone hosted by the stem can spread into toneless suffixes (§6.1.1); in addition, a H tone on a prosodic word can trigger tone deletion on the following word in certain environments (§§6.1.2–6.1.3).

– The Tonal Morpheme criterion: there is an inflectional tonal morpheme H on negated verbs (§7.1.2) and a derivational tonal morpheme H involved in one type of reduplication (§7.1.3).

The two contour tonemes have different realizations on words with different syllabic structure.

The **HL toneme** is realized as a falling contour on monosyllabic words: *ní* ‘water’, *ká*: ‘name.3SG.POSS’, *gál* ‘string bag’, *kái* ‘cry’.

In di- and polysyllabic words bearing the HL toneme, all non-final syllables have a H tone, but there is variation in the realization of tone on the final syllable.

When the final syllable is heavy, it receives a falling contour: *yópâl* ‘people’, *ámlâ*: ‘light’, *bñâ*: ‘rack for firewood’, *árwâi* ‘long’, *mól-ígwâl* ‘stay-2/3PL.LOC’.

When the final syllable is light, it is generally L-toned: *yópâ* ‘tree sp.’, *bñâ* ‘edge’, *ékí* ‘far’, *mól-gwâ* ‘stay-3SG.SRD’, *áráwâ* ‘pumpkin’, *dékópñ* ‘rainbow’.

Some CV-final forms show variation between the realization described above and another one, in which the final syllable is somewhat elongated and pronounced with a slight pitch rising

(roughly L-to-M): [HL *mol-wdae*] ‘stay-3SG.SRD’ [mol^wnldæ] ~ [mol^wnldæ:ʌ]; [HL *su-gwi*] ‘hit-3SG.DEM’ [ʃuŋlgwi] ~ [ʃuŋlgwi:ʌ], [HL *mol-imo*] ‘stay-3PL.PQM’ [molliɫmo] ~ [molliɫmo:ʌ]; [HL *e-ra-gwe*] ‘wear-FUT-3SG.IND’ [eɫraŋlgwe] ~ [eɫraŋlgwe:ʌ]. This variation is limited to a few (finite) verb forms and is likely due to an intonational effect (Tida 2006: 24).

Overall, surface realizations of the HL toneme are consistent with right-to-left mora-by-mora association: the L component docks to the word-final mora and the H component spreads across the rest of the span.

The tonemic status of HL is confirmed by the following criteria:

- The Non-Compositionality criterion: the HL contour combines H and L tonal levels, but there is no evidence for tonemic status of L.

- The Extensibility criterion: the HL tone can be realized on prosodic words of various length, including monosyllables (cf. §6.1.1 and examples just above).

- The Activity criterion: the HL tone hosted by the stem or verbal suffix can extend into other morphemes within the same prosodic word (§6.1.1).

The **LH toneme** likewise has a range of surface realizations which is overall similar to that of the HL toneme, but is not a perfect mirror image of it. On monosyllabic words, the LH toneme is realized as a rising contour. However, the rise doesn’t get all the way up to high pitch, unless there is a clitic following: [pr:ʌ] ‘fly.INF’, [ta:ʌ] ‘dawn.INF’, [kaiʌ] ‘needle’, [ɟgalʌ] ‘child’, but [ɟgalʌ=koɫpe] ‘child=PL’. This is the universal rule for phonetic realizations of the LH toneme: they start at low pitch and end somewhat higher, reaching high pitch only before a subsequent clitic.

On di- and polysyllabic words, the LH toneme is usually realized as a low pitch on non-final syllables and higher pitch on the final syllable: [eɫkɫɫ] ‘step.INF’, [aɫpaɫ] ‘bird’, [aɫpaɫ] ‘woman’, [aɫpaɫɫ] ‘sister.3SG.POSS’, [oɫmɫɫnaɫ] ‘eye.1SG.POSS’. Note that weight of the final syllable makes no difference here.⁶

Some words show variation between the realization described above and another one, in which there is a slight rise on the final syllable: [nullaiɫ] ~ [nullaiʌ] p.n., [aɫlauɫ] ~ [aɫlauʌ] ‘mistake’, [kurlwalɫ] ~ [kurlwalʌ] ‘be.crumpled.INF’. In all such cases, the final syllable starts with a sonorant and has either a diphthong or a consonantal coda. The phonetic effect is thus phonologically conditioned.

A few forms, on the contrary, obligatorily have a very slight fall on the last syllable (but again, a level high pitch when followed by a clitic): [naɫkalɫ] ‘what’, [joŋlgwalɫ] ‘put.3SG.LOC’. These are confined to the pronoun *nàkál* ‘what’ (from *nāl kāl* ‘what thing’) and locative relativizations, derived with the suffix *-kal*.

There is a replacive grammatical tonal morpheme LH carried by the Future suffix. When it is imposed on the whole form, its realization follows the rules outlined above, but the tonal span starts at the syllable containing the suffix, rather than at the left edge of the word: *pai*. [LH *nan*] [pai.nanʌ] ‘sleep.FUT.CONJ(DS)’, *pai*. [LH *ra.p!*] [pai.ra:ɫpɫ] ‘sleep.FUT.CONJ(DS)’. See §7.1.1 for details.

Overall, it looks like the LH toneme is associated from right to left syllable-by-syllable, but its final H component can dock to a consonantal mora when the syllable is apocoped.

The tonemic status of LH is confirmed by the following criteria:

- The Non-Compositionality criterion: the LH contour combines H and L tonal levels, but there is no evidence for tonemic status of L.

- The Extensibility criterion: the LH tone can be realized on prosodic words of various length, including monosyllables (cf. §6.1.1 and examples just above).

⁶ A kind of exception to this generalization is created by a low-level process of e-Apocope (§6.2.3).

– The Activity criterion: the LH tone hosted by the stem can extend into other morphemes within the same prosodic word (§6.1.1); in addition, a LH tone on a prosodic word can trigger tone deletion on the following word in certain environments (§§6.1.2–6.1.3).

– The Tonal Morpheme criterion: some person-number suffixes and the future suffix host a LH tone which can be extended on the entire prosodic word (§7.1.1).

3.3. Floating tones

There are no floating tones.

3.4. Downdrift and downstep

There is no explicit mention of downstep in (Tida 2006), but there are reasons to posit downdrift (automatic downstep) in Dom.

The final H component of a rising (LH) melody is regularly realized as mid-level pitch, rather than high, unless there is a clitic following (§3.2). Cf. [LH *gal*] [ʔgāl̄] ‘child’, [LH *apal*] [à.pāl̄] ‘woman’, [LH *aupale*] [àu.pà.lē] ‘sister’ (Tida 2006: 24–25). Since this phonetic lowering of H only ever occurs immediately after L, it is best viewed as downdrift.

3.5. Upstep

There is no upstep.

3.6. Other suprasegmental features of tonemes, apart from pitch. Interaction of tonemes and phonations. Registers

Tonemes in Dom have no features other than pitch. There are no discernible registers.

4. Tonotactics: tonal span, tonal phrase

4.1. Tonal span limits

4.1.1. Tonal span size

Tonal span generally coincides with a phonological word and never extends across word boundaries. Words in Dom are relatively short, even fully inflected verbs. A toneme minimally spans one monomoraic syllable, as in [H *ká*] ‘word’. The longest tonal span encountered in the annotated text is [LH *ka.r-i.pk.ra,e*], which is (5 morae across) 3 syllables.

4.1.2. Establishment of tonal span boundaries

Tonal Spread (§6.1.1) establishes a word-length tonal span. It can be seen as extending the toneme’s span beyond the boundaries of its host item.

Toneme Deletion rules (§6.1.2–6.1.3) eliminate a tonal span.

In verbal inflection, lexical toneme of the verb can be replaced with a grammatical tonal morpheme (§7.1.1), which usually fills the same span, though the LH tonal span created by the Future suffix may have its left boundary one or two syllables to the right from the left edge of the word.

4.1.3. Tonal spans and other units

Tonal span prototypically coincides with a phonological word. There are only two exceptions to their one-to-one correspondence:

1). Toneme Deletion rules (§6.1.2–6.1.3) eliminate a toneme, resulting in a phonological word with no tonal span: {[H *a.pal*] **gal**} woman child ‘girl’.

2). When the LH toneme supplied by the Future suffix is imposed on the word, its tonal span starts at the syllable containing the suffix, leaving the initial syllable(s) of the word outside of the tonal span: *ne.*-[LH *ra.-pŋ*] (§7.1.1).

4.2. Combinations of tonemes. Tonal melodies

There is never more than one toneme within the same phonological word.

4.3. Extratonal syllables

There are two cases in Dom in which extratonal syllables emerge: when non-initial prosodic word(s) (most often, clitics) in a tonal phrase are subject to one of the Toneme Deletion rules (§§6.1.2–6.1.3) and when the Future suffix imposes its LH toneme on a verb, leaving the first syllable outside of the tonal span. Tonalization of extratonal syllables proceeds differently in the two cases.

Clitics and other word divested of their tonemes by Toneme Deletion rules receive a default pitch pattern that starts somewhat lower than the preceding H and goes down. When the extratonal sequence is disyllabic, this is phonetically transcribed as a mid-level pitch on the first syllable (although it doesn't need to be exactly mid-level) and a low pitch on the second (8a–c). When only one syllable remains outside of the tonal span, it is usually transcribed with a mid-level pitch, although there is some variation (8d–g).

- (8) a. [aɭpaɭ=koɭpeɭ] ‘woman=PL’
b. [uɭ=kⁱ-pɭ-keɭ] ‘come=NEG-1DU-IND’
c. [eɭɭ=raɭ=waɭ] ‘like.this=MUT=ENC’
d. [paiɭ=kⁱɭɭ] ‘sleep=NEG.INF’
e. [aɭpaɭ ɳgaɭɭ] ‘woman child’ (=‘girl’)
f. [keɭpaɭ=jaɭɭ] ‘sweet.potato=and’
g. [jo-mɭ=iaɭ] ‘be-3SG=EXPL’ (Tida 2006: 33–36)

This default pitch pattern appears consistent with normal declination.

In Future verb forms, when the initial syllable is not included into the span of the LH toneme imposed by the suffix, it can be superficially realized with any pitch, from low to high, with no differences in meaning or acceptability: *kar-a-l* ‘see-FUT-1SG’ → *ka*._[LH raɭ] → [kaɭraɭɭ] ~ [kaɭraɭɭ] (Tida 2006: 25, 30–31).

4.4. Tonal phrases

Toneme Deletion rules (§§6.1.2–6.1.3) involve two adjacent prosodic words the second of which loses its toneme under the influence of the first. It appears reasonable to view the domain of application of these rules as a tonal phrase.

The following combinations of two prosodic words are thus postulated to constitute a tonal phrase:

- A host word + one of the clitics listed in (14) (even when the host word carries a HL toneme, so Clitic Toneme Deletion doesn't apply);
- a nominal modifier + a head noun (again, regardless of whether Phrasal Toneme Deletion actually applies);
- a reduplicated noun or adjective.

5. Stress and tone; culminativity; prominence; obligatoriness

5.1. Culminativity

Tone in Dom is culminative: no prosodic word can carry more than one toneme.

5.2. Stress

Dom has no stress.

5.3. Positional prominence

There is no positional prominence in Dom.

5.4. Obligatoriness of tone

Tone in Dom is not strictly obligatory, as Toneme Deletion rules (§§6.1.2–6.1.3) can eliminate a toneme on a prosodic word.

6. Tonal rules

6.1. Tonal rules

6.1.1. Tonal Spread

When a toneless suffix (or a tone-bearing suffix that fails to impose its toneme) is attached, the toneme supplied by the root is associated to the whole word, following the association rules presented in §3.2.

- (9) a. *ǒ-Ø* [o:ʌ] ‘hand.3SG.POSS’, *ǒ-n* [o:nʌ] ‘hand.2SG.POSS’, *ò-ná* [o:ɲnʌ] ‘hand.1SG.POSS’
b. *gúmà-Ø* ‘nose.3SG.POSS’, *gúmâ-n* ‘nose.2SG.POSS’, *gúmá-nà* ‘nose.1SG.POSS’
c. *kḡá-Ø* ‘knee.3SG.POSS’, *kḡá-n* ‘knee.2SG.POSS’, *kḡá-ná* ‘knee.2SG.POSS’ (Tida 2006: 37)
- (10) *ér* ‘wear.INF’, *érgwè* (< *er-m-ke*) ‘wear-2SG-IND’, *érigwè* (< *er-im-ke*) ‘wear-2/3PL-IND’
(Tida 2006: 88)

All nominal suffixes and most verbal suffixes are toneless. Some verbal suffixes carry their own LH toneme that can be imposed on the whole prosodic word, cf. §7.1.1 for details.

Note that this rule does not necessarily imply a spread of tone from one TBU to others. Rather, it simply reflects the fact that tonal association happens after all affixation.

6.1.2. Clitic Toneme Deletion

Most clitics lose their toneme when attached to a word carrying a H or LH toneme:

- (11) a. [HL *yal*] [H =*kope*] ‘men’
b. [LH *a.pal*] =*kope* ‘women’
c. [H *ge*] =*kope* ‘girls’ (Tida 2006: 33)

In (11a), the plural clitic =*kópé* follows a HL-toned word and retains its inherent H toneme. In (11b,c), a H-final (LH- or H-toned) host triggers deletion of toneme on the clitic.

When two clitics follow the same LH- or H-toned word, both lose their tonemes (12a). When a HL-toned word attaches two clitics, the first of which is LH- or H-toned, the second clitic has its toneme deleted (12b). When an affected clitic is inflected (only possible for =*k(ǐ)*- NEG, which has verb-like properties), subsequent suffixes likewise fall outside of any tonal span (13).

- (12) a. [LH *el*] =*ra* =*wa* ‘like.this=MUT=ENC’
b. [HL *dua*] [H =*la*] =*mer* ‘door=LOC=around’ (Tida 2006: 34)
- (13) [H *gl*] [H *ta*] [H *d*] =*kl-gwe*
strong NEG say=NEG-3SG.IND
‘It is not strong.’ (Tida 2006: 52)

The following clitics are affected by this rule:

- (14) a. HL: =*yâ* ‘and’, =*wé* ENC, =*wâ* ENC, =*bâ* ‘but’, =*iâ* EXPL. =*iô* EXPL
b. H: =*grá* ‘only’, =*dí* ‘that (DS)’, =*lá* LOC, =*râe* ‘that (MUT)’, =*káné* PL, =*kópé* PL, =*méré* ‘such as/around’
c. LH: =*kèné* ‘and (DS)’, =*k(ǐ)*- NEG (Tida 2006: 34–35)

- (19) a. *mol-ipl-ke* ‘stay-1DU-IND’
 b. *moiplke* root-final *l*-deletion
 c. *moipke* $l \rightarrow \emptyset / _k$
 d. *moipke* ~ *mepke* $o \rightarrow e / _i$ (?) (limited to verbs of this class, optional, environment provided by 2/3DU, 2/3PL)
 e. *moip.ke* ~ *mep.ke* syllabification (with diphthongization)
- (20) a. *mol-m-krae* ‘stay-3SG-MUT’
 b. *molgwrae* $mk \rightarrow gw$ [^hgw]
 c. *molgwrae* ~ *molwdae* $gwr \rightarrow wd$ (optional; only fed by the previous rule)
 d. *molgw.rae* ~ *molw.dae* syllabification

6.2.2. Metathesis

Some consonant sequences optionally exhibit metathesis: *pk* ~ *kp*, *kr* ~ *rk*, *pl* ~ *lp* (Tida 2006: 20). Tida characterizes these alternations as word-final, but his own examples do not fully corroborate this:

- (21) a. *dèpké* ~ *dèkpé* ‘dirty’, *mépkè* ~ *mékpè* ‘mountain’
 b. *gíkí⁸* *gókí’* ~ *gíké* *górké* ‘risp’
 c. *yópl̩* ~ *yôlp* ‘downside’, *ápl̩* ~ *álp* ‘flip side’

Since metathesis of this kind involves sonorants *r* and *l*, which in syllabification can be assigned to either onset, coda, or nucleus, depending on their position, it may have impact on the syllable structure. The form *yó.pl̩* ‘downside’ is disyllabic, but the case of its alternant *yôlp* is less clear. The discussion in (Tida 2006: 21) suggest it may be a monosyllable; if this is so, metathesis is able to produce exceptional CVCC monosyllables, of the structure otherwise restricted to non-final syllables of polysyllabic words. However, the wording in the source is too vague to be sure. Metathesized forms ending in *-lp*, *-rk* are not encountered in the annotated text.

6.2.3. e-Apocope

Tida (2006: 10) lists several optional rules that affect realization of a final *e* in native polysyllabic words:

- (22) a. $/e/ \rightarrow [o] / [+labial](C) _ \#$ (optional): *kólé* ~ *kóló* ‘part’, *àpé* ~ *àpó* ‘my father’
 b. $/e/ \rightarrow [\emptyset] / _ \#$ (optional)
 c. $/e/ \rightarrow \emptyset / _ \#$ (optional): *kóralè* ~ *kóral* ‘chicken’, *blé* ~ *bl̩* ‘his/her head’, *mólṁ=mó* ‘he stays, or?’ (< *mólmè=mô*)⁹

Of special interest is the deletion rule in (22c). Its application makes the prosodic word one syllable shorter (though the mora count is most often not affected). When a LH-toned word is affected by *e*-Apocope, it ends up with a rise on the final (C)VC syllable, which is prohibited under the normal association rules: [m̩ɲ̩.ɲ̩.ɲ̩eɲ̩] ~ [m̩ɲ̩.ɲ̩.ɲ̩] ‘smell’, [auɲ̩.palɲ̩eɲ̩] ~ [auɲ̩.palɲ̩] ‘sister.3SG.POSS’; contrast the last form with [aɲ̩.palɲ̩] ‘woman’. This suggest that unlike segmental rules mentioned and illustrated in the preceding subsections *e*-Apocope applies after syllabification and tone association; there is no re-mapping of tones after the final vowel is deleted.

⁸ Judging by the metathesized form *gíké*, the *i* in *gíkí’* is most probably epenthetic.

⁹ The apocopated variant is generally preferred before a clitic. It is explicitly claimed that *e*-Apocope only targets non-verbs (Tida 2006: 9–10), but subsequent text provides many examples to the contrary.

7. Grammatical and lexical tones

7.1. List of grammatical tonal morphemes

7.1.1. Replacive LH tonal morphemes in verbal inflection

While there are no grammatical distinctions expressed solely by tone, verbs in Dom may undergo tonal changes in addition to attachment of segmental suffixes. The resulting toneme on an inflected verb depends on its tonal class (§8.2), presence of the Future suffix, and the subject person-number; tonal patterns are thus consistent across different moods. Verbal paradigm for the Indicative (suffix *-ke*) is given in Table 3. For each tonal class, the first row shows non-Future forms, while the Future forms are in the second row. The morphological template is Root-(Future)-Person/Number-(Mood), although deletions, assimilations and other segmental changes may obscure morphemic boundaries.

For ease of reading, tonemes are shown in superscript at the left edge of their tonal spans. Shaded cells contain Future forms carrying a LH toneme whose tonal span is not left-aligned with the prosodic word; non-Future forms that show tonal changes are given in bold¹⁰.

	1SG (-Ø)	2SG (-n)	3SG (-m)	1DU (-pl)	2/3DU (-ipl)	1PL (-pn)	2/3PL (-im)
High: ^H <i>te</i> ‘give’	^{HL} <i>teke</i>	^{HL} <i>tege</i>	^{HL} <i>togwe</i>	^{HL} <i>topke</i>	^{HL} <i>teipke</i>	^{HL} <i>topge</i>	^{HL} <i>teigwe</i>
	^{HL} <i>terake</i>	^{HL} <i>tenage</i>	^{HL} <i>tenagwe</i>	^{te^{LH}}<i>rapke</i>	^{te^{LH}}<i>raipke</i>	^{te^{LH}}<i>rapge</i>	^{HL} <i>tenaigwe</i>
Falling- <i>r</i> : ^{HL} <i>er</i> ‘wear’	^{HL} <i>erke</i>	^{HL} <i>erge</i>	^{HL} <i>ergwe</i>	^{HL} <i>erpke</i>	^{HL} <i>eripke</i>	^{HL} <i>erpge</i>	^{HL} <i>erigwe</i>
	^{HL} <i>erake</i>	^{HL} <i>terage</i>	^{HL} <i>eragwe</i>	^{HL} <i>erapke</i>	^{HL} <i>eraipke</i>	^{HL} <i>erapge</i>	^{HL} <i>eraigwe</i>
Falling- <i>l</i> : ^{HL} <i>mol</i> ‘be, stay’	^{HL} <i>moke</i>	^{HL} <i>moge</i>	^{HL} <i>molgwe</i>	^{LH}<i>mopke</i>	^{LH}<i>meipke</i>	^{LH}<i>mopge</i>	^{HL} <i>moligwe</i>
	^{mol^{LH}}<i>ake</i>	^{mol^{LH}}<i>age</i>	^{mol^{LH}}<i>agwe</i>	^{mol^{LH}}<i>apke</i>	^{mol^{LH}}<i>aipke</i>	^{mol^{LH}}<i>apge</i>	^{mol^{LH}}<i>aigwe</i>
Rising: ^{LH} <i>pal</i> ‘put’	^{LH} <i>palke</i>	^{LH} <i>palge</i>	^{LH} <i>palgwe</i>	^{LH} <i>palpke</i>	^{LH} <i>palipke</i>	^{LH} <i>palpge</i>	^{LH} <i>paligwe</i>
	^{pal^{LH}}<i>ake</i>	^{pal^{LH}}<i>age</i>	^{pal^{LH}}<i>agwe</i>	^{pal^{LH}}<i>apke</i>	^{pal^{LH}}<i>aipke</i>	^{pal^{LH}}<i>apge</i>	^{pal^{LH}}<i>aigwe</i>

Table 3. Verbal paradigm in the Indicative (Tida 2006: 80)

The following generalizations can be made:

- verbs of the Falling-*r* class retain their lexical HL toneme in all forms;
- verbs of the Rising class carry a LH toneme in all forms, but in the Future the tonal span starts at the syllable containing the suffix, which is nearly always the second syllable of the verbal word, leaving the first syllable extratonal¹¹;
- verbs of the Falling-*l* class also carry a LH toneme with an exceptionally aligned tonal span in all Future forms, a normally aligned LH toneme in 1DU, 2/3DU and 1PL non-Future forms, and a HL toneme otherwise;
- verbs of the High class carry an exceptionally aligned LH toneme in 1DU, 2/3DU and 1PL Future forms, and a HL toneme otherwise.

Notably, tonal changes happen in the same person-number combinations in the Future of High verbs and in the non-Future of the Falling-*l* verbs. As Tida (2006: 80) remarks, the three subject cross-reference markers that appear to trigger the tonal change are those that contain /p/, which may not be a coincidence.

The tonal patterns of Dom verbs can in principle be accounted for in several different ways. Tida (2006: 80–81) offers an elegant solution, which is adopted below, restated in tonemic terms.

¹⁰ For verbs of the High tonal class, both H (found in the Infinitive and the same-subject Conjunctive) and HL (found in most inflected forms) are considered lexical tonemes, cf. 8.2.1 for details.

¹¹ There are several disyllabic verbs in the Rising class (like *pèràr-* ‘dig’) that, according to all the listed rules for allomorphy, segmental change and tonal association, should have two extratonal syllables at the left edge of their Future forms. However, no examples of any of these verbs in the Future have been found in the grammar.

- 1) Tonemes hosted by verbal roots are LH for the rising class, HL for the other three classes.
- 2) The Future suffix (*-a- ~ -ra- ~ -na-*) carries a LH toneme.
- 3) The *p*-containing agreement suffixes (*-pl* 1DU, *-ipl* 2/3DU, *-pn* 1PL) each carry a LH toneme.
- 4) All other verbal suffixes are inherently toneless.
- 5) When several toneme-hosting morphemes combine within one verbal word, only one toneme gets to be realized on the surface. The conflict is resolved according to the tonal class of the verb:
 - in the Falling-*r* class, only the toneme supplied by the root ever gets realized ($\tau_V > \tau_{FUT}, \tau_{PERS}$)
 - in the High class, the Future suffix gets to impose its toneme, but only in the presence of a toneme-bearing person/number suffix ($\tau_{FUT} + \tau_{PERS} > \tau_V > \tau_{FUT}, \tau_{PERS}$);
 - in the Rising class, the Future suffix always imposes its toneme; the lexical toneme is retained in its absence ($\tau_{FUT} > \tau_V > \tau_{PERS}$)¹²;
 - in the Falling-*l* class, both the Future suffix and a person/number can impose their toneme, with the former being dominant ($\tau_{FUT} > \tau_{PERS} > \tau_V$).

The effect of toneme-bearing suffixes on verbs of various classes can also be summarized in tabular form, as in Table 4. A “-” sign means that the toneme of the root is retained, while “+” indicates that LH toneme is imposed by either of the suffixes; “cross-*p*” stands for one of the cross-reference markers containing /p/.
- 6) When the LH toneme hosted by the Future suffix gets realized, its tonal span starts with the syllable containing the suffix, usually leaving the first (or perhaps the first two) syllable(s) unspecified for tone (§4.3.1).

class	FUT + cross- <i>p</i>	only FUT	only cross- <i>p</i>
Falling- <i>r</i>	-	-	-
High	+	-	-
Rising	+	+	-
Falling- <i>l</i>	+	+	+

Table 4. Tonal changes triggered by suffixes (Tida 2006: 81)

Thus, the Future suffix and the three above-listed subject cross-reference suffixes are postulated to have both a segmental and a tonal part. The latter involves a LH toneme in all cases, but in the case of the Future marker this toneme has an unusual tonal span. In the annotated text, I mark the tonemes hosted by these suffixes as grammatical. Strictly speaking, they are lexical tonemes hosted by grammatical morphemes that get associated with the entire prosodic word, including the root.

7.1.2. Replacive H tonal morpheme in negated verbs

Negated verbs have the structure Root=Negation-(Future)-Person/Number-(Mood). The Negative marker =*k(l)*- is best viewed as a negative verb with the whole range of inflection that cliticizes to a verbal root and takes it as a complement.

When attached to a HL verb, the Negative marker is said to change its toneme to H:

- (23) [H *yér*] [LH =*k-i-ke*] ‘remove=NEG-1SG-IND’ (*yêr*- ‘remove’) (Tida 2006: 34)

¹² Strictly speaking, it is not possible to determine whether the resulting toneme of 1DU, 2/3DU and 1PL non-Future forms comes from the root or the person-number suffix, since both carry LH with normal association properties. It is thus conceivable that the toneme realization rules for the Rising class are the same as those for the Falling-L class. However, if such an approach is adopted, the postulated tonal change would be vacuous.

Note that all HL verbs but one have roots that are able to form at most one full syllable (see §§8.2.2–8.2.3) and most of them upon attachment of the negative marker also undergo a segmental change that renders the root monomoraic. The tonal change may thus be a consequence of segmental shortening with the monomoraic root being unable to accommodate a tonal contour. Indeed, examples (24) strongly suggest that there is a variation in realization of tone tied to that in moraic structure which is not specific to the presence of the Negative marker:

- (24) a. [HL *mo,l*] [LH =*k-i.-ke*] ~ [H *mo*] [LH =*k-i.-ke*] ‘stay=NEG-1SG-IND’
 b. [HL *ya,l*] [H =*ko.pe*] ~ [H *ya*] [H =*ko.pe*] ‘man=PL’ (Tida 2006: 16)

However, as attested by (24) above, the tonal change is found even with bimoraic roots¹³. One may speculate that the tonal change originated in the restrictions of moraic structure, which concerned the majority of HL verbs, but later has been extended by analogy to the remaining handful that are bimoraic. There is only one relevant form in the annotated text ([H *mo*] [LH =*k-m*] [H =*d*] stay=NEG-1SG=QUOT ‘that I am not’), in which I do not annotate the initial H toneme as grammatical.

Note that as a clitic, the Negative marker is subject to Clitic Toneme Deletion (§6.1.2):

- (25) a. [H *ye,r*] [LH =*k-i.-ke*] ‘remove=NEG-1SG-IND’ (*yêr-* ‘remove’)
 b. [H *u*] =*k-p.-ke* ‘come=NEG-1PL-IND’ (*ú-* ‘come’)
 c. [LH *pa,i*] =*kl* ‘sleep=NEG-INF’ (*păi-* ‘come’)

While in (25a) the verb root changes its toneme to H, it doesn’t trigger the deletion of toneme on the clitic, contrast to an inherent H verb in (25b). The tonal change discussed in this subsection should thus be preceded (and counterfed) by that of Clitic Toneme Deletion.

When the Negative is combined with the Future, it carries a LH toneme, but it is not entirely clear if the latter comes from the clitic or from the suffix, since the Negative clitic doesn’t contain enough phonological material to form an extratonal syllable, cf. [H *mo*] [LH =*kl-a-l*] ‘stay=NEG-FUT-1SG’ (Tida 2006: 203). I assume that the toneme in such cases is supplied by the suffix, per standard rules for Rising verbs (see previous subsection). It must be noted, however, that judging by the transcription used by Tida, such combinations are still subject to Clitic Toneme Deletion: [H *s*] =*kl-a-m* ‘hit=NEG-FUT-3SG’ (Tida 2006: 203)

7.1.3. Replacive H tonal morpheme in reduplication

Word reduplication in Dom is sometimes accompanied with a tonal change in the first element (lexical toneme replaced with H) and/or segmental change(s) in the second element (the first vowel (or, in case of diphthongs, the first component thereof) is turned to *a* and/or the initial consonant changed to *m*). In reduplications of some words both kinds of changes are present:

- (26) a. *àwá* ‘getting inverted’ → *áwá màwá*
 b. *díu* ‘shaking’ → *díu dâu*
 c. *gúp* ‘getting cut’ → *gúp máp* (Tida 2006: 38)

Since the first element in such cases is segmentally faithful and the second element is tonally faithful, it is not a straightforward question which one should be considered the reduplicant and which one the base. Tida (2006) opts to gloss the second element as RDP and I follow suit here.

¹³ Among the HL verbs, there is one exceptional verb with disyllabic root: *dawal-* ‘to put together’. While no examples of it under negation are given in the grammar, it is listed among the relevant verbs in (Tida 2006: 82) right before the generalization about the tonal change in question is introduced.

This pattern is most characteristic of state-denoting words that are only used as complements of light verbs, as in (26). However, some bipartite lexemes superficially appear as frozen reduplications of this kind, e.g. *kúim kǎim* ‘butterfly’, *gǎ gǎ* ‘spiky grass.’ The H toneme on the first element can be analyzed as a derivational replacive tonal morpheme. However, there is only one example of reduplication within the annotated text (*nú náu* ‘pushing.RDP’) and it is not clear if it really involves a tonal change, since the reduplicated word inherently carries a H toneme to begin with.

7.2. Tonal paradigms

Not relevant.

7.3. Lexical tones

Dom has lexical tones. Every lexical root in the language hosts a toneme.

7.4. Toneless morphemes

While a few verbal suffixes can be argued to host a LH toneme (§7.1.1), all nominal and most verbal suffixes in Dom are inherently toneless (Tida 2006: 37, 41). Toneless suffixes are included into the tonal span projected by the root or a tone-bearing affix (§6.1.1, (§7.1.1)).

8. Tonal classes of words

8.1. Differentiation of parts of speech by tone

There is no differentiation of parts of speech by tone. A prosodic word of any part of speech can carry either of the three tonemes.

8.2. Tonal classes of words (beyond the parts of speech distinctions)

Simple verbs in Dom are a closed part of speech, with only about 140 members. The majority of them fall into four classes with distinct tonal behavior.

8.2.1. The High class

This class comprises 8 verbs, all of them having monomoraic roots¹⁴:

(27) a. *s-* ‘hit’, *d-* ‘say’, *p-* ‘go’

b. *i-* ‘get’, *u-* ‘come’

c. *te-* ‘give’, *de-* ‘burn’, *ne-* ‘eat’ (Tida 2006: 81)

These verbs have a H toneme in the Infinitive and in the same-subject Conjunctive form with *-re*, but a HL toneme in all other forms except when the Future suffix imposes its LH toneme. This is the only class in which the default toneme for conjugated forms is different from that of the bare root form. One may speculate that underlyingly these verbs carry a HL toneme which gets simplified to H in the monomoraic Infinitive, but this doesn’t explain its occurrence with the Conjunctive; besides, in all other case when a contour tone has to be associated to a monomoraic unit, Dom employs vowel lengthening rather than contour simplification. I still annotate both H and HL for this class as lexical tonemes.

The verb *p-* ‘go’ is the only suppletive verb in Dom. It is *p-* in the H-toned forms, *e-* in other non-Future forms, and *na-* in the Future. Since in the last case the root effectively merges with the Future suffix, it is also the only verb in Dom (besides the negator =*kl*, cf. §7.1.2) whose Future forms do not contain an extratonal syllable in the beginning when the LH toneme of the suffix takes over, cf. [LH *na.-pn*] ‘go.FUT-1PL’ vs. *d.-*[LH *ra.-pn*] ‘say-FUT-1PL’.

¹⁴ Note that not all monomoraic verbs of Dom belong to this class, there are at least a few in the Rising class as well; contrast *ú-* ‘come’ and *ũ-* ‘put over the fire’.

8.2.2. The Falling-*r* class

This is the smallest class with only 5 verbs. Four of them are monosyllabic and have a root-final *-r*, but one is exceptional:

- (28) a. *er-* ‘wear/move’, *yer-* ‘remove’, *kor-* ‘discard/leave’, *gur-* ‘pull’
b. *dawal-* ‘put together’ (Tida 2006: 81)

Semantically, they all seem to be related to movement/manipulation, though this may be a coincidence.

These verbs carry a HL toneme (which can only be replaced by a H toneme imposed by the negative clitic, per 7.1.2). It is thus the most resilient tonal class, where the lexical toneme can not be overwritten by that of a suffix, even in the Future forms with appropriate cross-reference markers.

8.2.3. The Falling-*l* class

This class comprises 18 verbs that carry a HL toneme and end in *-l* in the Infinitive:

- (29) a. *pl-* ‘hear’, *bl-* ‘get drenched’, *gl-* ‘put into a bag’
b. *pol-* ‘take out’, *bol-* ‘fight, suffer’, *mol-* ‘be, stay’, *kol-* ‘fill’, *gol-* ‘die’,
c. *pal-* ‘chop’, *bal-* ‘cut’, *dal-* ‘call’, *kal-* ‘bite’, *gal-* ‘roast, burn’, *yal-* ‘plant’
d. *kul-* ‘bear, look after’, *gul-* ‘be slack’
e. *el-* ‘make’, *pel-* ‘dig’ (Tida 2006: 82)

This root-final *-l* is deleted in some person/number forms. This truncation mostly appears morphologically, rather than phonologically, conditioned. Opposite to its sister Falling-*r* class, this is the class most susceptible to tonal change, with the presence of either the Future or a *p-* containing cross-reference marker sufficient to overwrite the lexical toneme.

8.2.4. The Rising class

This is the largest class comprising about 3/4 of Dom’s verbal lexicon. Some examples are given in (30) (see (Tida 2006: 246–247) for the full list).

- (30) a. *ta-* ‘dawn’, *nu-* ‘whet’, *ye-* ‘put’
b. *gr-* ‘draw in’, *kn-* ‘put on a shoulder’, *dl-* ‘uproot’
c. *pai-* ‘sleep’, *wau-* ‘dig’, *geu-* ‘curve’, *eul-* ‘chop’,
d. *kan-* ‘see’, *bin-* ‘assemble’, *mal-* ‘seethe with’
e. *tomn-* ‘wear out’, *ekl-* ‘step’, *kupr-* ‘get wrenched’
f. *perar-* ‘dig’ (Tida 2006: 83)

As the examples show, it is also the most phonologically diverse class, containing verbs with segmental shapes characteristic of the other classes. In fact, all known minimal pairs for tone composed of verbal infinitives contain one verb from the Rising class and one from either the High (cf. fn.14 above) or the Falling-*l* class (31). All disyllabic verbs except *dawal-* and all verbs containing diphthongs also belong to this class.

- (31) a. *pĭ* ‘hear.INF’, *pĭ* ‘pluck.INF’
b. *kūl* ‘bear, look after.INF’, *kūl* collect.INF’
c. *mōl* ‘be, stay.INF’, *mōl* ‘put on.INF’ (Tida 2006: 245)

Verbs of the Rising class always carry a LH toneme, but in the Future its tonal span starts with the syllable containing the temporal suffix (in all person-number combinations), as befits the grammatical toneme imposed by the latter. Presumably, non-Future forms retain the lexical toneme, though this is disputable, since there is no way to distinguish between the lexical LH toneme carried by verbs of this class and that supplied by the *p*-containing cross-reference markers.

8.2.5. Other

The defective verb *man-* ‘not be’ falls outside of the four classes delineated above. It is only found in a limited number of forms, all of which carry a H toneme.

9. Diachrony of tone

No tonal reconstruction for the Simbu language group is available. Word-level tonal distinctions exemplified by Dom appear typical for Simbu languages, but the inventory of tonemes and the direction of their association may vary (see (Hardie 2003; Evans et al. 2005; Rarrick 2017) and references therein).

10. Tonal notation in the writing

10.1. Presentation of tones in (local) linguistic tradition

Tida (2006: 26) distinguishes three word-level phonological tones in Dom which correspond straightforwardly to the three tonemes identified herein: high (H), falling (HL), and rising (LH). Chao tone letters after each syllable are used to indicate pitch in phonetic transcriptions, while in phonological transcription, tones are marked with inverse Chao tone letter before a word/tonal span.

10.2. Tonal notation in the writing

There is no practical orthography for Dom.

11. Calculation of the Tonal Density Index

The TDI has been calculated on the basis of the folk tale ‘Frog’ (Tida 2006: 255–260), the first of the six glossed texts provided in Appendix C of the grammar. Dom tales start and end with ritual phrases *kér kér dí î* and *kúpá áipà bí tól=tál*, signalling the beginning and the end of the story respectively. These are not used in conversation and appear not to be synchronically divisible into meaningful lexical items. Since their prosodic realization is said to vary (Tida 2006: 255, fn.1), they were excluded from the text as presented here.

In deviation from the standard practice of the present project, the text is represented in a two-line rather than three-line format, with the phonological representation omitted. The transcription employed in (Tida 2006) uses word-level tone letters that correspond one-to-one to our tonemes. The line of phonological representation would thus be essentially identical to that of standard tonemic annotation, with only notational differences.

Clitic boundaries are not specifically marked in the annotation line, as clitics are considered full-fledged prosodic words, but the “=” symbols are used in the glosses line for convenience of a human reader. In the vertical format, the “=” symbol is substituted with “≡”, so that the Excel program would not recognize the gloss for a clitic as a formula.

Unfortunately, in his representation of texts in Appendix C, Tida (2006: 255–288) for some reason does not mark the effects of toneme deletion rules. While Clitic Toneme Deletion (§6.1.2) is straightforward to apply, Prasal Toneme Deletion (§6.1.3) presents a more problematic case. First, its conditions make reference to syntactic structure, which is not always evident: do the two nouns in e.g. *gāl súl* child two.person ‘two children’ stand in a head-modifier relation? Second, the formulation in (Tida 2006: 36) suggests that application of this rule is optional. I thus chose to consider a toneme deleted only in those cases that have been cited in the main text of the grammar,

where toneless units are explicitly marked as such. This issue is relevant for calculation of tonal density, but regardless of the decision, the TDI (currently at 0.69) would fall between 0.68 ((if Prasal Toneme Deletion is applied in all suspicious cases) and 0.71 (if said rule is ignored totally).

[LH gal] [H ta] {[HL yal] [LH gal]} [H ta] [LH yo.go]
 child =INDEF man child another and
 {[LH a.pal] gal} [H ta] [LH yo.go] [LH ne-m] [HL go.l-m] [HL du.-gwe]
 woman child another and father-3SG.POSS die-3SG say-3SG.IND
 ‘The father of a boy and a girl died.’

[HL go.l-m] [H ia] [HL yal] [H sul] {[HL i] [H rae]} [HL mol] [HL e-ip.ka]
 die-3SG =EXPL man two.person DEM =MUT stay.INF go-2/3DU.SRD
 ‘These two lived by themselves.’

[HL taim] [H ta] {[H i] ra we} [LH gal] [LH tau]
 time =INDEF DEM =MUT =ENC.WE child some
 [H u.-re] [LH yel] [HL du-m] [HL du.-gwe]
 come-CONJ(SS) like.this say-3SG say-3SG.IND
 ‘One day some children came to their house and said this.’

[LH no.ne] [H nul] [HL du] [H ku] [HL e.l-e]
 1NSG.INC river frog catch (make)- CONJ(SS)
 [HL bus] [LH ku.na] [H i] [H ka] [LH ko.pa] [H s-r.e] e.<[LH l-a-p.ga]>
 bush around DEM bird bird hit-CONJ(SS) make-FUT-1PL.SRD
 [H er] [HL si] [HL su.-gwal] {<[LH na.-pn]> wa} [HL du-m] [HL du.-gwe]
 to be.bush (hit)-3SG.LOC go.FUT-1PL =ENC.WA say-3SG say-3SG.IND
 ‘Let’s go to the bush to catch frogs by the river and catch birds in the woods.’

[HL du.-gwa] [LH gal] [H sul] {[HL i] [H rae]} [H dul]
 say-3SG.SRD child two.person DEM =MUT follow
 [HL bol.-gwa] [H er] [HL e-im] [HL du.-gwe]
 (be.hit)-3SG.SRD to go-2/3PL say-3SG.IND
 ‘The two children followed them and all of them went out.’

[H er] [H pi] [HL si] [HL su.-gwal] [H p-r.e] [H ka] [LH ko.pa] [H si]
 to go.INF be.bush (hit)-3SG.LOC go-CONJ(SS) bird bird hit.INF
 [H er] [HL e-iw.dae] [H ka] [LH ko.pa] [HL wai] [HL su.-dae]
 to (hit)-3SG.LOC bird bird good hit-3SG.MUT
 [LH ne-m] [HL kui] [HL mol.-gwa] [LH gal] [H te.-re] [H ka] [LH ko.pa]
 father-3SG.POSS alive stay-3SG.SRD child give-CONJ(SS) bird bird
 [H ki] {[HL mol.-gwa] [HL ya]} [H ka] [LH ko.pa] [HL gol.-gwa] [HL kap] [H si]
 bad stay-3SG.SRD =and bird bird die-3SG.SRD animal hit.INF
 [LH ne-m] [HL gol.-gwa] [LH gal] [H sul] {[HL i] [H rae]}
 father-3SG.POSS die-3SG.SRD child two.person DEM =MUT

[HL *to-m*] [HL *du.-gwe*]
give-3SG say-3SG.IND

‘They went to the bush catching birds, but when they caught good birds they gave them to a child whose father was still alive and when they caught bad quality birds or dead birds, they gave them to the two children whose father had died.’

[HL *to-m*] [H *ia*] [HL *yal*] {[H *sul*] *ae*} [LH *au.-re*] [LH *au.-re*]
give-3SG =EXPL man two.person =MUT hold-CONJ(SS) hold-CONJ(SS)

[HL *e.l-e*] [HL *kol*] [LH *ba.l-o*] [HL *du.-gwa*]
make-CONJ(SS) road cut.one’s.way-IMP.SG say-3SG.SRD

[HL *kol*] [LH *bal.-go*] [H *er*] [HL *e-im*] [HL *du.-gwe*]
road cut.one’s.way-3SG.CONJ(DS) to go-2/3PL say-3SG.IND

‘The two children taking the birds, cut their way through the bush as the other children told them to do and they all went on their way.’

[H *er*] [H *pi*] [H *pi*] [H *ba*] [H *i*] {[HL *e-im*] [HL *ba*]} [LH *gal*]
to go.INF go.INF halfway DEM go-2/3PL =but child

[LH *ne-m*] [HL *kui*] [HL *mol.-gwa*] {[LH *gal*] *ae*} [HL *el*] [HL *mol*]
father-3SG.POSS alive stay-3SG.SRD child =MUT make.INF stay.INF

[LH *ne-m*] [HL *gol.-gwa*] [LH *gal*] {[HL *i*] [H *rae*]} [H *ne*] [H *s-r.e*]
father-3SG.POSS die-3SG.SRD child DEM =MUT hit hit-CONJ(SS)

[H *s-r.e*] [LH *au*] [H *nu*] [H *nau*] [H *s-r.e*] [HL *e.l-m*] [HL *du.-gwe*]
hit-CONJ(SS) hold.INF push RDP (hit)-CONJ(SS) make-3SG say-3SG.IND

‘On their way the children whose fathers were still alive hit and pushed around those two whose father had died.’

[HL *e.l-m*] [H *ia*] [LH *gal*] {[H *sul*] *ae*} [HL *kai*] [HL *el*]
make-3SG =EXPL child two.person =MUT cry make.CONJ(SS)

[HL *el*] [H *pi*] [H *ba*] [H *i*] [HL *e-ipk.rae*] [H *p-r*]
make.CONJ(SS) go.INF halfway DEM go-2/3DU.MUT go-CONJ(SS)

[LH *ka.r-ipk.rae*] [H *no.man*] [LH *mel*] [LH *kin*] [H *s-r.e*] [HL *el*]
see-2/3DU.MUT think a.lot.of very hit-CONJ(SS) make.INF

[H *pi*] [H *nul*] [HL *e-ipk.rae*] [H *p-r.e*] [LH *ka.r-ipk.rae*]
go.INF river go-2/3DU.MUT go-CONJ(SS) see-2/3DU.MUT

[HL *du*] [H *ge.ml*] [HL *por*] [H *ta*] [HL *mo.l-m*] [HL *du.-gwe*]
frog black.frog big =INDEF stay-3SG say-3SG.IND

‘Crying, the two children arrived at a place and looked around. Feeling sad, they arrived at a river, where they saw a huge black frog.’

[HL *mo.l-m*] [H *ia*] [HL *yal*] {[H *ku.na*] *rae*} {[HL *or.pl*] [H *di*]}
stay-3SG =EXPL man age.sake =MUT quickly =QUOT

[H *pi*] [LH *gal*] [LH *ne-m*] [HL *gol.-gwa*] {[LH *gal*] *rae*}
go.INF child father-3SG.POSS die-3SG.SRD child =MUT

[HL *or.pl*] [H *di*] { [H *pi*] { [HL *du*] [H *rae*] } [HL *su.-dae*] [HL *ko.re*]
 quickly =QUOT go.INF frog =MUT hit-3SG.MUT but
 { [HL *du*] [H *rae*] } [LH *yel*] [HL *du-m*] [HL *du.-gwe*]
 frog =MUT like.this say-3SG say-3SG.IND
 ‘As the child whose father had died nimbly caught the frog, the frog said this.’

[H *wa.-na*] [H *o*] [HL *a.pl.-a*] [H *o*]
 son-1SG.POSS =VOC daughter-1SG.POSS =VOC
 ‘My son, my daughter!’

[H *en*] { <[LH *me-i.pl*] > [HL *ba*] }
 you stay-2/3DU =but
 [LH *gal*] [LH *ne-m*] [HL *kui*] [HL *mol.-gwa*] [LH *gal*] [LH *ku.na*] [HL *i.me*]
 child father-3SG.POSS alive stay-3SG.SRD child around down.there
 [H *en*] [HL *ma.pn*] [HL *el*] [H *en*] [HL *to.-gwe*] [H *ki*] [LH *ka.r-i*] *ya*
 you behaviour make.INF you say-3SG.IND bad see-1SG =EXPL
 ‘I do not approve of what the children whose fathers are still alive did to you.’

[H *na*] [H *en*] [LH *kan*] { [HL *mol*] [HL *ua*] } [H *ta*] [LH *kan*]
 1EXC you see.INF stay.1SG =ENC.WA NEG see.INF
 { [H *mo*] [LH *k-m*] *d* }
 stay =NEG-3SG =QUOT
 ‘I am watching you. Do not think that I am not watching you.’

[H *na*] [H *en*] [LH *kan*] [HL *mo.-ka*] [HL *el.-gwi*] [H *na*] [H *ki*]
 1EXC you see.INF stay-1SG.SRD make-3SG.DEM 1EXC bad
 [HL *pl*] [H *a*] [HL *ko.re*] { [HL *el.mai*] [HL *we*] } [H *en*]
 perceive.1SG =PERM but now =ENC.WE you
 [H *p-r*] [LH *pa.re*] [LH *i.ke*] [LH *ke*] [LH *pa-ip.ka.l*] [LH *ik*] [LH *mul*]
 go-CONJ(SS) =and(SS) house build.INF lie-2/3DU.LOC house back
 { [HL *ip*] [H *rae*] } { *ka*.<[LH *r-a-i.pl*] > *ba* } [HL *ko.re*] [HL *gal*] [HL *bek*]
 up.there =MUT see-FUT-2/3DU =but but string.bag bag
 [HL *ka.ma*] [H *ta*] [LH *yo.-gwi*] [LH *au*] [H *kul*] [H *d-il.l-o*]
 black =INDEF be-3SG.DEM hold.INF raise (say)-DU-IMP
 [HL *du-m*] [HL *du-gw*]
 say-3SG say-3SG.IND
 ‘I felt bad because of what happened while I was watching you. You go home and you will find a black bag at the back of your house. Take it,’ said the frog.’

[HL *du-m*] [H *ia*] [LH *gal*] { [H *sul*] *ae* } { [HL *du.-gwa*] [H *me.re*] }
 say-3SG =EXPL child two.person =MUT say-3SG.SRD =as/about
 [HL *kai*] [HL *el*] [HL *e.l-e*] [H *mn*] [HL *bl*]

cry (make).CONJ(SS) (make)-CONJ(SS) lament (smear).CONJ(SS)
 [HL *kai*] [HL *eI*] [HL *e.l-e*] [H *er*] [HL *w-ip.ka*] [HL *w-ip.ka*]
 cry (make).CONJ(SS) (make)-CONJ(SS) to come-2/3DU.SRD come-2/3DU.SRD
 [LH *ik*] [LH *ke*] [LH *pa-ip.ka.l*] [LH *ik*] [LH *mul*] {[HL *i*] [H *rae*]}
 house build.INF lie-2/3DU.LOC house back DEM =MUT
 [H *u.-re*] [LH *ke.pa*] [LH *wau*] [HL *yu-ip.ka*] [HL *bal*] [HL *gal*]
 come-CONJ(SS) sweet.potato dig.INF fetch-2/3DU.SRD chop.INF burn(tr).INF
 [HL *gal*] [HL *er*] [H *ne.re*] [LH *al*] [HL *no.-gwa*]
 burn(tr).INF and eat-CONJ(SS) brother.3SG.POSS eat-3SG.SRD
 [LH *au.pal*] [HL *to.-gwa*] [HL *no.-go*] [HL *el.-gwa*]
 sister.3SG.POSS give-3SG.SRD eat-3SG.CONJ(DS) make-3SG.SRD

‘They walked back home as they were told, crying, missing their father. They came to the back of their house. They peeled the sweet potatoes which they had dug and carried them home, cooked and ate them. The brother ate and gave some to his sister and she ate.’

[H *ul*] {*pai*.<[LH *-ra.-pl*> *di*} [HL *eI*] [LH *pa.re*]
 sleep lie-FUT-1DU =QUOT make.CONJ(SS) =and(SS)
 [H *u*] [HL *me.na*] [H *pi*] {[LH *ka.n-m*] *ba*} [LH *ik*] [LH *mul*]
 come.INF outside go.INF see-3SG =but house back
 {[HL *i*] [H *rae*]} {[H *kl.e*] *di*} [HL *gal*] [HL *bek*] [HL *ka.ma*] [H *ta*]
 DEM =MUT silently =QUOT string.bag bag black =INDEF
 [LH *yo-m*] [HL *du-gw*]
 be-3SG say-3SG.IND

‘Before they went to sleep, they went out to look and there really was a black bag at the back of the house.’

[HL *gal*] [HL *bek*] [HL *ka.ma*] {[LH *yo.-gwi*] *rae*} [LH *au*] [H *kul*]
 string.bag bag black be-3SG.DEM =MUT hold.INF raise
 [HL *du.-dae*] [LH *au*] [H *kul*] [H *d-r.e*] [LH *kan-w.dae*]
 (say)-3SG.MUT hold.INF raise (say)-CONJ(SS) see-3SG.MUT
 [HL *mo.ni*] [H *i.la*] [HL *i*] [LH *pa-m*] [HL *du.-gwe*]
 money inside DEM lie-3SG say-3SG.IND

‘They lifted the black bag which was there. They lifted [it], looked [into it] and found money in it.’

[HL *mo.ni*] [LH *mel*] [LH *kin*] [HL *wo.ne*] [HL *tau.sen*] [HL *tau.sen*] [LH *pa.-gwa*]
 money a.lot.of very truly thousand thousand lie-3SG.SRD
 [LH *gal*] {[H *suI*] *ae*} [H *i*] [LH *ye.-re*] [HL *suI*] [H *d-r.e*]
 child two.person =MUT take.INF put-CONJ(SS) school (say)-CONJ(SS)
 [HL *eI*] [HL *e-ip.ki*] [H *pi*] [HL *sa.we*] [LH *pa.-gwa*] [H *si*] [H *ne.re*]
 make.INF make-2/3DU.DEM go.INF knowledge lie-3SG.SRD hit.INF eat-CONJ(SS)
 [LH *gal*] [LH *ne-m*] [HL *kui*] [HL *mol.-gwa*] [LH *gal*] {[HL *i*] [H *rae*]}
 child father-3SG.POSS alive stay-3SG.SRD child DEM =MUT

[HL *bo.i*] <[LH *ku-i.pl*]> [HL *du.-gwe*]
hired.man look.after-2/3DU say-3SG.IND

‘A lot of money, thousands and thousands, was in the bag. The two children kept the money, received an education, and when they graduated, they became successful and hired the children whose fathers were alive as servants.’

[HL *s.to.ri*] [LH *ye,l*] [HL *di.-ka*] [HL *wa,i*] [HL *su.-gwe*]
story like.this say-1SG.SRD end (hit)-3SG.SRD
‘This is the end of my story.’

Glosses

CONJ – conjunctive
DEM – demonstrative
DU – dual
ENC.WA – clause-final enclitic =*uà*/*wà*
ENC.WE – phrase-final enclitic =*wê*
EXC – exclusive
EXPL – explicative
FUT – future
IMP – imperative
IND – indicative
INDEF – indefinite article
INF – infinitive
LOC – locative / locative relativization
MUT — mutual knowledge
NEG — negation
NMLZ — nominalization
PL – plural
PERM – permissive
POSS – possessive
PQM – polar question marker
QUOT – quotative
RDP – reduplication
SG – singular
SRD – subordinative
SS – same subject
VOC – vocative

References

- Eberhard, David M., Gary F. Simons & Charles D. Fennig (eds.). 2024. *Ethnologue: Languages of the World*. 27th edn. Dallas, TX: SIL International. <http://www.ethnologue.com>.
- Evans, Nick, Jutta Besold, Hywel Stoakes, Alan Lee, Robyn Loughnane, Belinda Ross & Kate Brown. 2005. *Materials on Golin: grammar, texts and dictionary*. The Department of Linguistics and Applied Linguistics, The University of Melbourne. <http://hdl.handle.net/11343/33836>. (27 January, 2025).
- Hardie, Peter. 2003. *Is Kuman tonal? An account of basic segmental and tonological structure in the Papuan language Kuman*. Canberra: Australian National University MA.

- Rarrick, Samantha Carol. 2017. *A Tonal Grammar of Kere (Papuan) in Typological Perspective*. ProQuest LLC. Mānoa: University of Hawai'i at Mānoa. (27 January, 2025).
- Tida, Syuntarô. 2000. *Domugo no tôn ni kansuru kôsatu [On the tone of the Dom language]*. Kyoto: Kyoto University MA Thesis.
- Tida, Syuntarô. 2006. *A grammar of the Dom language: A Papuan Language of Papua New Guinea*. Kyoto: Kyoto University PhD.
- Tida, Syuntarô. 2012. Tonal evidence for subgrouping the Simbu dialects. Paper presented at the History, contact and classification of Papuan languages, 2-3 Feb 2012, Amsterdam.
- Xu, Yi & Xuejing Sun. 2002. Maximum speed of pitch change and how it may relate to speech. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America* 111(3). 1399–1413.
<https://doi.org/10.1121/1.1445789>.
- Zhang, Jie. 2013. *The Effects of Duration and Sonority on Countour Tone Distribution: A Typological Survey and Formal Analysis*. New York: Routledge.
<https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315024134>.